

SIMULATION OF CERTAIN POWER QUALITY ISSUES: VOLTAGE SAGS, HARMONICS & TRANSIENT

A Thesis

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CERTIFICATE

Certified that this is a bonafide record of the dissertation work entitled, “**SIMULATION OF CERTAIN POWER QUALITY ISSUES: VOLTAGE SAGS, HARMONICS & TRANSIENT**”, done by **B.S.R.K.VARMA** bearing Admn. No: (08001D0715) submitted to the faculty of Electrical Engineering, in partial fulfillment of the requirements for the Degree of **MASTER OF TECHNOLOGY** with specialization in **ELECTRICAL POWER SYSTEMS** from Jawaharlal Nehru Technological University College of Engineering (Autonomous), Anantapur.

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CHAPTER I
INTRODUCTION

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INTRODUCTION

1.1 INTRODUCTION

The term *Power Quality* has become one of the most prolific buzzword in the power industry since the late 1980s. The issue in electricity power sector delivery is not confined to only energy efficiency and environment but more importantly on quality and continuity of supply or Power Quality and supply quality. Both electric utilities and end users of electrical energy are becoming increasingly concerned about the quality of electric power. Electrical Power Quality is the degree of any deviation from the nominal values of the voltage magnitude and frequency. Power Quality may also be defined as the degree to which both the utilization and delivery of electric power affects the performance of electrical equipment. From the customer perspective, Power Quality problem is defined as any power problem manifested in voltage, current, or frequency deviations that result in power failure or misoperation of customer of equipment [1].

Power Quality problems concerning frequency deviation are the presence of harmonics and other departures from the intended frequency of the alternating supply voltage. On the other hand, Power Quality problems concerning voltage magnitude deviations can be in the form of voltage fluctuations, especially those causing flicker. Other voltage problems are the voltage sags, short interruptions and transient over voltages. Transient over voltage has some of the characteristics of high-frequency phenomena. In a three-phase system unbalanced voltages also is a Power Quality problem [2]. Among them, three Power Quality problems have been identified to be of major concern to the customers are voltage sags, harmonics and transients this project will be focusing on these three problems and their mitigation.

Figure: 1.1 describes the demarcation of the various Power Quality issues defined by IEEE Std. 1159-1995. [2]

Figure 1.1: Demarcation of the various Power Quality issues defined by IEEE Std. 1159-1995[2]

Three factors that are driving interest and serious concerns in Power Quality are [1]:

- i. Newer generation load equipment, with microprocessor based controls and power electronic devices, is more sensitive to Power Quality variations, than was equipment used in the past.
- ii. The increasing emphasis on over all power system has resulted in continued growth in the application of devices such as high efficiency, adjustable speed motor drives and shunt capacitors for power factor correction and to reduce losses. This is resulting in increasing harmonic levels in power systems and has many people concerned about the future impact on system capabilities.
- iii. End users have an increased awareness of Power Quality issues. Utility customers are becoming better informed about such issues as interruptions, sags, and switching transients, and are challenging the utilities to improve the quality of power delivered.

- iv. In industries many things are interconnected in a work. Integrated process means that the failure of any component has much more important consequences.

1.2 PROBLEM FORMULATION

With the increased use of sophisticated electronics, high efficiency variable speed drive, power electronic controllers and also more & more non-linear loads Power Quality has become an increasing concern to utilities and customers. Voltage sag is the most common type of Power Quality disturbance in the distribution system. It can be caused by fault in the electrical network or by the starting of a large induction motor. Although the electric utilities have made a substantial amount of investment to improve the reliability of the network, they cannot control the external factor that causes the fault, such as lightning, often called as “Acts of God”.

Many dips are caused by faults on the supply network with the severity of the dip depending on the relative positions of the generator, fault and measurement point. One study, carried out by a major generator, measured voltage disturbances at 12 sites with demand between 5 and 30 MVA. In a ten-month period 858 disturbances were logged, 42 of which resulted in disruption and financial loss. Although all 12 sites were low technology manufacturing operations making low value added products the financial loss totaled 600,000 € (average 14,300 per event or 50,000 per site), with the highest individual loss of 165,000 €. Clearly plants making high value added products and those requiring multistage manufacturing processes, such as semiconductors, would face much higher losses. Table-1 below gives some typical values [5].

It is estimated that Power Quality problems cost industry and commerce in the EU about 10 billion € per annum while expenditure on preventative measures is less than 5 % of this [5].

In general, voltage sags can causes:

- i. Motor load to stall/stop
- ii. Digital devices to reset causing loss of data
- iii. Equipment damage and/or failure
- iv. Materials spoilage

- v. Lost production due to downtime
- vi. Additional costs
- vii. Product reworks
- viii. Product quality impacts
- ix. Impacts on customer relations such as late delivery and lost of sales
- x. Cost of investigations into problem

INDUSTRY	TYPICAL FINANCIAL LOSS PER EVENT
Semiconductor production	€ 3 800 000
Financial Trading	€ 6 000 000 per hour
Computer centre	€ 7 50 000
Telecommunications	€ 30 000 per minute
Steelworks	€ 3 50 000
Glass industry	€2 50 000

Table 1.1: Costs of Power Quality problems

In the same way nonlinear type loads contribute to the degradation in the electric supply's Power Quality through the generation of harmonics. The increased use of nonlinear loads makes the harmonic issue (waveform distortion) a top priority for all equipment manufacturers, users and electric utilities. Severe power system harmonics are usually the steady state problem not the transient or intermittent type and these harmonics can be mitigated by using harmonic filters. Lower order harmonics cause the greatest concern in the electrical distribution/utilization system.

- i. Capacitors may draw excessive current and prematurely fail from increased dielectric loss and heating.
- ii. Harmonics may interfere with telecommunication systems, especially noise on telephone lines.

- iii. Transformers, motors, and switchgear may experience increased losses and excessive heating.
- iv. Induction motors may refuse to start (cogging) or may run at subsynchronous speeds.
- v. Circuit breakers may fail to interrupt currents owing to improper operation of blowout coils.
- vi. The time–current characteristics of fuses can be altered and protective relays may experience erratic behavior. In particular, maloperation of the relays associated with ripple control systems can occur.

Harmonics interfere with sensitive-type electronic communications and networks.

The economic effects of harmonics are shorter equipment lifetime, reduced energy efficiency and a susceptibility to nuisance tripping.

There are several defined measures commonly used for indicating the harmonic severity and content of a waveform. One of the most common measures is total harmonic distortion in current (I_{THD}) & voltage (V_{THD}).

$$I_{THD} = \left[\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} I_n^2}}{I_1} \right] \text{-----} (1.1)$$

Where I_1 : Fundamental (50Hz) Current; n: Harmonic order and I_n : Harmonic current

$$V_{THD} = \left[\frac{\sqrt{\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} V_n^2}}{V_1} \right] \text{-----} (1.2)$$

Where V_1 : Fundamental (50Hz) Voltage; n: Harmonic order and V_n : Harmonic voltage

Transients are voltage disturbances of very short duration (up to a few milliseconds) but high magnitude (up to several thousand volts) with a very fast rise time. Most transients arise from the effects of lightning strikes or switching of heavy or reactive loads. Because of the high frequencies involved they are considerably attenuated as they propagate through the network so that those occurring close to the point of interest will be much larger than those originating further away. Protective devices in the

network ensure that transients are generally kept to a safe level and most problems arise because the source of the transient is close to or within the installation.

The damage that results may be instantaneous, such as the catastrophic failure of electrical plant or appliances, or the corruption of data within computers or on network cabling or it may be progressive with each event doing a little more damage to insulation materials until catastrophic failure occurs. The cost of replacing the failed equipment and the cost of the downtime involved must be considered. Protection is relatively cheap. The basic requirement is that the installation earthing system should be designed to have low impedance over a wide frequency band, with a good low impedance connection to the earth electrode system. The lightning protection system should be designed appropriately, taking into account local factors, such as the number of lightning days per year. Transient protection should be fitted at the entry of all incoming conductors, including telephone and other communications lines. The manufacturer should have provided suppression of transients from switching equipment and good maintenance procedures should be introduced to ensure that it continues to be effective [6].

On average the absolute share of impacts of the different categories of disturbances is as follows [7]:

Disturbance	Percentage
Voltage dips	23.6%
Short interruptions	18.8%
Long interruptions	12.5%
Harmonics	5.4%
Surges and transients	29%
Other	10.7%

Table 1.2: Share of impacts of the different categories of disturbances

These shares can be further summarized as:

- i. Voltage dips are the most important source of impacts in the continuous manufacturing sector.
- ii. Short interruptions are most significant for food, metallurgy and newspaper publishing.

- iii. Long interruptions are most costly for hotels and other public service sectors.
- iv. Surges and transients are most destructive for the telecommunications sector and for the pharmaceutical sector.

This project focuses on major Power Quality issues such as voltage sags, swells, harmonics and transients; intends to investigate mitigation technique that is suitable for different type of voltage sags, filter design for reducing harmonic distortion and surge arrester sizing and location for transients.

1.3 OBJECTIVE OF THE THESIS

The objectives of this project are:

- i. To investigate suitable mitigation techniques for different type of Power Quality issues.
- ii. To simulate and analyze the techniques using MiPower software for improving Power Quality.
- iii. To observe the effectiveness of Static VAR Compensator (SVC), Distribution STATIC COMPensator (DSTATCOM), passive harmonic filter and Surge arrester in improving Power Quality.
- iv. To make a few suggestions on the suitability of such techniques used for Power Quality issues

1.4 PROJECT SCOPE

The scope for the project is:

- i. Mitigation techniques that will be studied
 - a. Static VAR Compensator (SVC),
 - b. Distribution static compensator (DSTATCOM),
 - c. Passive harmonic filters,
 - d. Surge arrester.
- ii. All techniques will be tested on different type of loads.
- iii. Analysis will focus on effectiveness of each technique in mitigating the power Quality issues.

1.5 ORGANIZATION OF THE THESIS

The complete thesis is divided into 6 chapters. In this, chapter 1 discusses about the power quality and the available solutions followed by literature survey for Power Quality issues in chapter 2.

Chapter 3 describes about the MiPower software package: software used to conduct simulations in this thesis and its windows, Chapter 4 of the thesis summarizes the solutions to different Power Quality problems in the form of custom power devices, harmonic filters, and surge arrestors.

In Chapter 5, the modeled SVC, DSTATCOM, Harmonic filter, and Surge arrester is applied to a study system and the results show that the SVC, DSTATCOM can mitigate the voltage sags and fluctuations successfully; harmonic filter reduces the harmonic distortion in the system and surge arrester reduces the effect of transients. This chapter also shows the simulation results with the SVC, DSTATCOM, Harmonic filter, and Surge arrester. The Simulation work is completed using MiPower version 6.0

Finally in Chapter 6, discussed conclusions and future scope of work.

CHAPTER II

POWER QUALITY ISSUES

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POWER QUALITY ISSUES

2.1 INTRODUCTION

In an electrical power system, there are various kinds of Power Quality disturbances. They are classified into categories and their descriptions are important in order to classify measurement results and to describe electromagnetic phenomena, which can cause Power Quality problems. Some disturbances come from the supply network, whereas others are produced by the load itself. The categories can be classified below

- i. Short-duration voltage variations
- ii. Long-duration voltage variations
- iii. Transients
- iv. Voltage imbalance
- v. Waveform distortion
- vi. Voltage fluctuation
- vii. Power frequency variations

2.2 SHORT-DURATION VOLTAGE VARIATIONS

There are three types of short-duration voltage variations, namely, instantaneous, momentary and temporary, depending on its duration. Short-duration voltage variations are caused by fault conditions, energization of large loads, which require high starting currents or loose connections in power wiring. Depending on the fault location and the system conditions, the fault can generate sags, swells or interruptions. The fault condition can be close to or remote from the point of interest. During the actual fault condition, the effect of the voltage is of short-duration variation until protective devices operate to clear the fault.

2.2.1 Sag

A sag (also known as dip) is a reduction to between 0.1 and 0.9 pu in rms voltage or current at the power frequency for a short period of time from 0.5 cycles to 1 min [3]. A 10% sag is considered an event during which the RMS voltage decreased by 10% to 0.9 pu. Voltage sags are widely recognized as among the most common and important aspects of Power Quality problems affecting industrial and commercial customers. They are particularly troublesome. Since they occur randomly and are difficult to predict.

Voltage sags are normally associated with system faults on the distribution system, sudden increase in system loads, lightning strikes or starting of large load like induction motors. It is not possible to eliminate faults on a system. One of the most common causes of faults occurring on high-voltage transmission systems is a lightning strike. When there is a fault caused by a lightning strike, the voltage can sag to 50% of the standard range and can last from four to seven cycles. Most loads will be tripped off when encounter this type of voltage level. Possible effect of voltage sags would be system shutdown or reduce efficiency and life span of electrical equipment, particularly motors.

Equipment sensitivity to voltage sag occurs randomly and has become the most serious Power Quality problem affecting many industries and commercial customers presently. An industrial monitoring program determined an 87% of voltage disturbances could be associated to voltage sags. Most of the faults on the utility transmission and distribution system are single line-to-ground faults (SLGF).

Figure 2.1: Voltage sag due to a single line-to-ground fault [3].

2.2.2 Swell

A swell (also known as momentary overvoltage) is an increase in rms voltage or current at the power frequency to between 1.1 and 1.8 pu for durations from 0.5 cycle to 1 min [4]. Swells are commonly caused by system fault conditions, switching off a large load or energizing a large capacitor bank. A swell can occur during a single line-to-ground fault (SLGF) with a temporary voltage rise on the unfaulted phases. They are not as common as voltage sags and are characterized also by both the magnitude and duration. During a fault condition, the severity of a voltage swell is very much dependent on the system impedance, location of the fault and grounding. The effect of this type of disturbance would be hardware failure in the equipment due to overheating.

Figure 2.2: Voltage swell caused by a line-to-ground fault [3].

2.2.3 Interruption

An interruption occurs when there is a reduction of the supply voltage or load current to less than 0.1 pu for duration not exceeding 1 min [3]. Possible causes would be circuit breakers responding to overload, lightning and faults. Interruptions are the result of equipment failures, power system faults and control malfunctions. They are characterized by their duration as the voltage magnitude is always less than 10% of the nominal. The duration of an interruption can be irregular when due to equipment malfunctions or loose connections. The duration of an interruption due to a fault on the utility system is determined by the utility protective devices operating time.

Figure 2.3: An interruption of approximately 0.17 seconds duration [3].

2.3 LONG-DURATION VOLTAGE VARIATIONS

Long-duration variations can be either overvoltages or undervoltages. They contain root-mean-square (rms) deviations at power frequencies for a period of time longer than 1 min [3]. They are usually not caused by system faults but system switching operations and load variations on the system.

2.3.1 Overvoltages

An overvoltage is defined as an increase in the rms ac voltage greater than 110% at the power frequency for duration longer than 1 min [3]. Overvoltages can be the result of switching off a large load, energizing a capacitor bank or incorrect tap settings on transformers. These occur mainly because either the voltage controls are inadequate or the system is too weak for voltage regulation. Possible effect could be hardware failure in the equipment due to overheating.

2.3.2 Undervoltage

An undervoltage (also known as brownout) is defined as a decrease in the rms ac voltage to less than 90% at the power frequency for a period of time greater than 1 min [3]. Undervoltage is the result of switching on a load, a capacitor bank switching off or overloaded circuits. Possible effect include system shutdown. Most electronic controls are very sensitive as compared to electromechanical devices, which tend to be more tolerant.

2.4 TRANSIENTS

Transients can be classified into two categories, namely, impulsive and oscillatory. These terms reflect the wave shape of a current or voltage transient.

2.4.1 Impulsive Transient

An impulsive transient is defined as a sudden, non-power frequency change in the steady-state condition of voltage, current, or both, which is unidirectional in polarity (either positive or negative) [3]. Impulsive transients are usually measured by their rise and decay times and also their main frequency. Lightning is the most common cause of impulsive transients. The shape of impulsive transients can be changed quickly by circuit components and may have different characteristics when viewed from different parts of the power system when high frequencies are involved. Impulsive transients can even stimulate the natural frequency of power system circuits and produce oscillatory transients.

Figure 2.4: Impulsive transients due to lightning strike [3].

2.4.2 Oscillatory Transient

An oscillatory transient describes as a sudden, non-power frequency change in the steady-state condition of voltage, current, or both, which includes positive and negative polarity values [3]. It consists of a voltage or current whose instantaneous value changes

polarity rapidly. They are characterized by its duration, magnitude and main frequency. A back-to-back capacitor energization result in oscillatory transient currents is termed a medium frequency transient. Medium frequency transients can also be the result of a system response to an impulsive transient. Depending on the type of loads, worst case could cause voltage spikes that break insulation somewhere in the system.

Capacitor switching, which associated with transient, is a daily utility operation to correct the power factor. Many heavy industrial loads such as induction motors and furnaces operate at low power factor. Heavy inductive loads cause excess current to flow in the lines, which increase losses. The effects include equipment damage or failure, process equipment shutdown and computer network problems.

Installation of capacitor banks can save energy and improve on the system security. A reduction in power loss and an improved voltage profile can be achieved when capacitors are dynamically controlled to changes in the feeder's load. These benefits depend on how capacitors are sized, placed and in controlled so that savings are maximized.

In general, the total capacity of capacitor banks is approximately 50% of the total generating capacity in a typical power distribution system. The factors that affect the transient magnitude and characteristics are source strength, transmission lines, other transmission system capacitor banks and switching devices. Pre-insertion resistors and synchronous closing are some of the techniques that involved in the reduction of capacitor switching transients.

Figure 2.5: An oscillatory transient due to capacitor bank switching

The capacitor voltage is not possible to change instantaneously when energization of a capacitor bank occurs. This results in a sudden drop of system voltage towards zero, followed by a fast voltage overshoot and finally an oscillating transient voltage imposed on the 50 Hz waveform. Depending on the instantaneous system voltage at the moment of switching, the peak voltage magnitude can reach two times the normal system peak voltage under severe conditions. Typical distribution system overvoltages due to capacitor switching range from 1.1 - 1.6 pu with transient frequency ranging from 300 – 1 kHz.

Oscillatory transients with frequencies less than 300 Hz can also be found on the distribution system. They are associated with ferroresonance and transformer energization. Some common methods to limit transient overvoltages on the DC bus of sensitive equipments are:

- i. Arrange a reactor in series with AC input terminal.
- ii. Use of Static VAR Compensators (SVCs) in the distribution systems.

2.5 VOLTAGE IMBALANCE

Voltage imbalance (or unbalance) is a condition in which the maximum deviation from the average of the three-phase voltages or currents, divided by the average of the three-phase voltages or currents, expressed in percentage [3]. Voltage imbalance can be the result of blown fuses in one phase of a three-phase capacitor bank. Severe voltage imbalance greater than 5% can cause damage to sensitive equipments.

Figure 2.6: Voltage imbalance

2.6 WAVEFORM DISTORTION

Waveform distortion is a condition whereby a steady-state deviates from an ideal sine wave of power frequency characterized by the main frequency of the deviation. There are generally five types of waveform distortion, namely, dc offset, harmonics, interharmonics, notching and noise.

2.6.1 DC Offset

DC offset is the presence of a dc current or voltage in an ac power system. This can occur due to the effect of half-wave rectification [3]. Direct current found in alternating current networks can have a harmful effect. This can cause additional heating and destroy the transformer.

2.6.2 Harmonics

Harmonics are a growing problem for both electricity suppliers and users. A harmonic is defined as a sinusoidal component of a periodic wave or quantity having a frequency that is an integral multiple of the fundamental frequency usually 50 Hz or 60 Hz [3]. Harmonic refers to both current and voltage harmonics. Harmonic voltages occur as a result of current harmonics, which are created by electronic loads. These nonlinear loads will draw a distorted current waveform from the supply system. The amount of current distortion is dependent upon the kVA rating of the load, the types of load and the fault level of the power system at the point where the load is connected.

Industrial loads like electric arc furnaces, and discharge lighting can cause harmonic distortion. The effect of harmonics in the power system includes the corruption and loss of data, overheating or damage to sensitive equipment and overloading of capacitor banks. The high frequency harmonics may also cause interference to nearby telecommunication system.

Fourier analysis can be used to describe distortion in terms of fundamental frequency and harmonic components from a given distorted periodic waveform. By using this technique, we can consider each component of the distorted wave separately and apply superposition. Using the Fourier series expansion, we can represent a distorted periodic waveshape by its fundamental and harmonic: It is also common to use a single

quantity, the Total Harmonic Distortion (THD) as a measure of the effective value of harmonic distortion. The development of Current Distortion Limits is to:

- i. Reduce the harmonic injection from each single consumer so that they will not cause unacceptable voltage distortion levels for normal system characteristics.
- ii. Restrict the overall harmonic distortion of the system voltage supplied by the utility.

The harmonic distortion caused by each single consumer should be limited to an acceptable level and the whole system should be operated without existing harmonic distortion. The harmonic distortion limits recommended here provide the maximum allowable current distortion for a consumer.

2.6.3 Interharmonics

Interharmonics are defined as voltages or currents having frequency components that are not integer multiples of the frequency at which the supply system is designed to operate [3]. The causes include induction motors, static frequency converters and arcing devices. The effects of interharmonics are not well known.

2.6.4 Notching

A periodic voltage disturbance caused by normal operation of power electronics devices when current is commutated from one phase to another is termed notching [3]. Notching tends to occur continuously and can be characterized through the harmonic spectrum of the affected voltage. The frequency components can be quite high and may not be able to describe with measurement equipment used for harmonic analysis.

Figure 2.7: Notching in a three-phase rectifier

2.6.5 Noise

Noise is unwanted distortion of the electrical power signals with high frequency waveform superimposed on the fundamental [3]. Noise is a common source by electromagnetic interference (EMI) or radio frequency interference (RFI), power electronic devices, switching power supplies and control circuits. Noise disturbs electronic devices such as microcomputer and programmable controllers. Use of filters and isolation transformers can usually solve the problem.

2.7 VOLTAGE FLUCTUATION

Voltage fluctuation is defined as the random variations of the voltage envelope where the magnitude does not exceed the voltage ranges of 0.9 to 1.1 pu [3]. Flicker usually associates with loads that display continuous variations in the load current magnitude causing voltage variations. The flicker signal is measured by its rms magnitude expressed as a percent of the fundamental whereas voltage flicker is measured with respect to the sensitivity of human eye. It is possible for lamp to flicker if the magnitudes are as low as 0.5% and the frequencies are in the range of 6 to 8 Hz. One common cause of voltage fluctuations on utility transmission and distribution system is the arc furnace.

Figure 2.8: Voltage fluctuations

2.8 POWER FREQUENCY VARIATIONS

Any deviation of the power system fundamental frequency from its nominal value (usually 50 or 60 Hz) is defined as power frequency variations [3]. The power system frequency is associated with the rotational speed of the generators supplying the system. The size and duration of the frequency shift depends on the load characteristics and the response of the generation control system to load changes. As the load and generation changes, small variations in frequency occur.

Frequency variations can be the cause of faults on power transmission system, large load being disconnected or a large source of generation going off-line. Frequency variations usually occur for loads that are supplied by a generator isolated from the utility system. The response to sudden load changes may not be sufficient to adjust within the narrow bandwidth required by frequency sensitive equipment. Possible effect could result in data loss, system crashes and equipment damage.

2.9 VOLTAGE TOLERANCE CRITERIA

Manufacturers of computers and data-processing equipment do not generally publish data informing the user of the voltage tolerance limits for their equipment. An agency known as the Information Technology Industry Council (ITIC) has published a graph that provides guidelines as to the voltage tolerance limits within which information technology equipment should function satisfactorily. The ordinate (y-axis) represents the voltage as a percentage of the nominal voltage. The abscissa (x-axis) is the time duration

in seconds (or cycles). The graph contains three regions. The area within the graph is the voltage tolerance envelope, in which equipment should operate satisfactorily. The area above the graph is the prohibited region, in which equipment damage might result. The area below the graph is the region where the equipment might not function satisfactorily but no damage to the equipment should result. The figure 2.9 shows the ITIC curve [6].

Figure 2.9: Information Technology Industry Council (ITIC) graph

CHAPTER III
MiPower SOFTWARE

CHAPTER III

MiPower SOFTWARE

3.1 INTRODUCTION

For performing the simulation works and studies MiPower software package has been used. MiPower is a highly interactive, user friendly windows based power system analysis package. It includes a set of modules for performing a wide range of power system design and analysis study. MiPower features include a top notch windows GUI with centralized database.

In MiPower we can conduct following analysis.

- i. Load Flow Analysis
- ii. Short Circuit Analysis
- iii. Distance Relay Co-ordination
- iv. Overcurrent Relay Co-ordination
- v. Transient Stability
- vi. Dynamic Stability
- vii. Sub Synchronous Resonance
- viii. Network Reduction
- ix. Voltage Instability
- x. Harmonic Analysis
- xi. Overvoltage Studies
- xii. Three Phase Load Flow Analysis

Here a brief description of the tools which are used in this project work are given

3.2 LOAD FLOW ANALYSIS

POWERLFA is designed to perform the steady state load flow analysis for the given system. Fast Decoupled load flow algorithm is used to solve the nonlinear power flow problem. Sparse storage and matrix ordering techniques are used in the program to reduce the memory requirements. Fast computational methods are made used to speed up the execution. Generation and load regulation characteristics are considered in the model

to determine the new system steady state frequency at which the loads and generation are balanced.

Study Info

The general load flow options are to be selected by the user

Figure 3.1: Load flow study Window

3.3 TRANSIENT STABILITY ANALYSIS

POWERTRIS is designed to perform the transient stability analysis for the given power system. The transient behavior of a power system, resulting from major disturbances such as a fault followed by switching operations, sudden rejection of load or generation, etc., is referred as Transient Stability. Transient stability solution is obtained in time domain. Transient stability simulation studies are carried out to study these phenomena and the results enable to plan and coordinate the protection and control schemes efficiently. Critical clearing times of circuit breakers can be computed and protection zones of distance relays during transient swings can be adjusted. Proper restoration/islanding schemes can be suitably designed. Compared to load flow and short

circuit studies, transient stability studies are more complex since they involve the electromechanical dynamics of rotating machines and their associated controls viz., excitation and governor systems. The period of investigation varies from fraction of a second when first swing stability is being determined, to over several seconds when multiple swing stability is to be examined.

The program requires the base case load flow solution to establish the initial conditions. The program uses fast Decoupled load flow method for the network solution, and implicit trapezoidal rule of integration method for the solution of differential equation representing the dynamics of machines, controllers, etc.

Study Info

On clicking study info a dialog box is displayed with various control options for transient stability analysis.

The following are the informations required for transient stability analysis.

Figure 3.2: Transient stability study window

List of Disturbances

- i. Change in transformer parameters
- ii. Change in transmission line parameters
- iii. Change in real and reactive power of loads
- iv. Simulation of Three Phase to ground fault
- v. Change in number of generator sets at a bus
- vi. Total generation outage at a bus
- vii. Simulation of single line to ground fault
- viii. Loss of excitation at a generator
- ix. Change in Shunt Impedance Load
- x. Change in Load Model

3.4 HARMONIC ANALYSIS

POWERHAR is designed to perform the harmonic study for the given system. Sparse storage and matrix ordering techniques are used in the program to reduce the memory requirements. Fast computational methods are employed to speed up the execution. Program performs the 3 phase harmonic Load Flow to compute the harmonic distortion factors.

Study Info

On clicking study info a dialog box is displayed with the necessary control options for harmonic analysis.

Figure 3.3: Harmonic study window

3.5 OVER VOLTAGE ANALYSIS

POWERETA module is designed to perform the overvoltage studies for the given system. Using POWERETA, it is possible to study the overvoltages arising out of -

- i. Switching operations
- ii. Different types of faults
- iii. Lightning surges

Power systems may be subjected to overvoltages that may be of transient or of persistent nature. Normally power systems are subjected to two types of overvoltages

- i. Overvoltages having atmospheric origin and,
- ii. Overvoltages generated due to internal causes within the power system.

The overvoltages of atmospheric or external origin are called as ‘Impulse overvoltages’ and those of internal origin are called ‘Switching overvoltages’ and ‘Temporary overvoltages’. Overvoltages stress the insulation of the power system equipment beyond safe limits, leading to equipment failure. Hence it is essential to study overvoltage phenomenon in the power system and their effects on the system.

The transient phenomena occur on a scale of microseconds (e.g., initial transient recovery voltage), milliseconds (e.g., switching surges), or cycles (e.g., Ferro-resonance). The system must be designed to withstand these overvoltages with a certain probability, or their effects must be reduced and limited with protective devices. The simulation of transient phenomena is therefore important for proper insulation co-ordination, as well as for the proper design of protection schemes. Simulation studies are needed to investigate interference in neighboring communication lines, or hazardous coupling effect to personnel, livestock and equipment.

Study Info

Study info pops up a dialog box in which the data to be given for the study will be entered. Here there are two options, Over Voltage Studies and Output Options

Over Voltage Studies

Over Voltage Studies | Output Options

Fault Type: No Fault | Impulse Source Info >> | Fault Bus Number: []

Fault Details

Ground to Neutral Resistance	0 pu	Ini. Res. value when switch closed	0.001 pu
Phase to Neutral Resistance	0.001 pu	Res. value when switch opened	999.99 pu
Pre-insertion Resistor Value	0.25 pu	Res. value when switch closed	0.001 pu

Switching Info. | Consider Magnetizing data for Transformer

Switching and Pre-insertion Timings

Phase A Closing with Resistor	0.002 sec
Phase B Closing with Resistor	0.004 sec
Phase C Closing with Resistor	0.008 sec
Ph A Pre-insert. Res. Shorting	0.01 sec
Ph B Pre-insert. Res. Shorting	0.012 sec
Ph C Pre-insert. Res. Shorting	0.014 sec

Tolerance for

Phase A Pole Opening	0.002 pu
Phase B Pole Opening	0.002 pu
Phase C Pole Opening	0.002 pu

Fault Initiation Voltage at

Phase A	0.005 pu
Phase B	0.005 pu
Phase C	0.005 pu

OK | Cancel | Apply

Figure 3.4: Overvoltage study window

Figure 3.5: Overvoltage study window –plot options

3.6 FREE PROGRAMMABLE BLOCKS (FPB)

Free programmable block is one module of MiPower software which allows user defined control blocks to be added to the network. The model of various kinds of dynamic control blocks like AVR, governors, all the FACTS devices on the system can be analyzed. The various components of control block is described to software by using elementary functions such as integrator, adder, multiplier, switch and simple non-linear functions.

For incorporating SVC and DSTATCOM in to the system these model were designed using FPB.

CHAPTER IV
POWER QUALITY MITIGATION TECHNIQUES

CHAPTER IV

POWER QUALITY MITIGATION TECHNIQUES

4.1 INTRODUCTION

There are different solutions to mitigate Power Quality problems. The solution adopted will be tailored specifically to the problem and site.

The measures used in this project to deal with Power Quality disturbances are

- Static VAR Compensator (SVC)
- Distribution static compensator (DSTATCOM)
- Passive harmonic filters
- Surge arrestors

4.2 STATIC VAR COMPENSATOR

The SVC is a shunt device of the flexible a.c. transmission system (FACTS) family using power electronics to control reactive power flow. The term static is used to differentiate SVCs from rotating var compensators (synchronous motors or generators). The SVC regulates the voltage at its terminals by controlling the amount of reactive power injected into or absorbed from the power system. When the system voltage is low, the SVC generates reactive power (capacitive behavior). In doing so, the demand of reactive power of the load is provided by the SVC and the feeding lines are relieved from transporting it. As a result, the voltage drop decreases and the voltage at the load terminals increase. Similarly, when the system voltage is high, the SVC absorbs reactive power (inductive behavior) [7].

CIGRE defines a static var system (SVS) as a combination of a static var compensator (SVC) and mechanically switched capacitors and reactors, all under coordinated control [8].

4.2.1 Basic Description of Static Var Compensator

There are two types of SVC:

1. Fixed Capacitor-Thyristor Controlled Reactor (FC-TCR)
2. Thyristor Switched Capacitor - Thyristor Controlled Reactor (TSC- TCR).

The second type is more flexible than the first one and requires smaller rating of the reactor and consequently generates fewer harmonics. The schematic diagram of a TSC- TCR type SVC is shown in Figure. 4.1. This shows that the TCR and TSC are connected on the secondary side of a step-down transformer. Tuned and high pass filters are also connected in parallel which provide capacitive reactive power at fundamental frequency. The voltage signal is taken from the high voltage SVC bus using a potential transformer.

The TSC is switched in using two thyristor switches (connected back to back) at the instant in a cycle when the voltage across valve is minimum and positive. This results in minimum switching transients. In steady state, TSC does not generate any harmonics. To switch off a TSC, the gate pulses are blocked and the thyristors turns off when the current through them fall below the holding currents. It is to be noted that several pairs of thyristors are connected in series as the voltage rating of a thyristor is not adequate for the voltage level required. However the voltage ratings of valves for a SVC are much less than the voltage ratings of a HVDC valve as a step down transformer is used in the case of SVC. To limit di/dt in a TSC it is necessary to provide a small reactor in series with the capacitor [10].

Figure 4.1: Typical static var system [10].

4.2.2 Concept of Static VAR Compensator

The control of the SVC is based on measuring the reactive component of the load current and deciding the firing angle in such a way that the SVC injects or absorbs the amount of reactive power required for compensation. At the instant of voltage zero crossing, the load current $i(t)$ is measured. At this instant, the active component of the load current is zero since the active current component is in phase with the voltage wave. Therefore, the current measured at the instant of voltage zero crossing is equal to the reactive component of the load current. In this way, the reactive current measured in a certain half cycle is used to determine the firing instant of the thyristors in the following half cycle. In doing so, the current through the reactance (in the case of a TCR) is regulated and the total reactive current injected by the converter can also be controlled.

One of the main limitations of this kind of control to compensate rapid fluctuations is the inherent delay of its operation mode. There is a time interval between the instant of measuring the reactive component (in one half cycle) and the firing instant

(in the following one). Once triggered, thyristor valves must remain conducting until natural commutation occurs. On the other hand, it is important to take into account that the SVC can accurately control the current fundamental component, but it produces harmonic components. For this reason, generally, it is necessary to install filters in order to reduce the harmonic content introduced in the network by the compensation system.

As a first approximation, SVCs are considered cost effective for large installations above around 50 MVA. The flicker attenuation factor that can usually be achieved by means of these compensators is between 1.5 and 2 [7].

4.2.3 V-I characteristics of Static VAR Compensator

The steady state control characteristics of SVC are shown in Figure. 4.2, where ADB is the control range. OA represents the characteristic where the SVC hits the capacitor limit, BC represents the SVC at its inductor limit. Note that SVC current is considered positive when SVC susceptance is inductive. Thus

$$I_{SVC} = -B_{SVC} V_{SVC} \quad \text{----- (4.1)}$$

Thus SVC is made up of 3 segments corresponding to

(i) If $V > V_{\max}$: $B_{SVC} = -B_L = -\frac{1}{X_L}$

(ii) Control range

(iii) If $V < V_{\min}$: $B_{SVC} = B_C = \frac{1}{X_C}$

The slope of OA is B_C (susceptance of the capacitor) and the slope of OBC is B_L (susceptance of the reactor). A positive slope (in the range of 1-5%) is given in the control range to

- a) Enable parallel operation of more than one SVC connected at the same or neighboring buses and
- b) Prevent SVC hitting the limits frequently.

Figure 4.2: Control characteristic of SVC

The steady state value of the SVC bus voltage is determined from the intersection of the system characteristic and the control characteristic. The system characteristic is a straight line with negative slope and is defined by

$$V_{SVC} = V_{Th} - X_{Th}I_{SVC} \quad \text{----- (4.2)}$$

Where V_{Th} and X_{Th} are the Thevenin voltage and reactance viewed from the SVC bus.

Figure 4.3: Determination of operating point of SVC

The SVC control range is described by

$$V_{SVC} = V_{ref} + X_S I_{SVC} \quad \text{----- (4.3)}$$

Where X_S is the slope of the control characteristic. V_{ref} is the SVC voltage corresponding to point D) when $I_{SVC} = 0$.

4.2.4 Applications of Static VAR Compensator

The application of SVC was initially for load compensation of fast changing loads such as steel mills and arc furnaces. The application for transmission line compensators commenced in the late seventies. The applications of SVC include:

1. Increase power transfer in long lines
2. Improve stability with fast acting voltage regulation
3. Damp low frequency oscillations due to swing (rotor) modes
4. Damp subsynchronous frequency oscillations due to torsional modes
5. Control dynamic overvoltages

A SVC has no inertia compared to synchronous condensers and can be extremely fast in response (2-3 cycles). This enables the fast control of reactive power in the control range.

4.2.5 Modeling of Static VAR Compensator

SVC application studies require appropriate power system models and study methods covering the particular problems to be solved by the SVC application. A functional block diagram representation of the SSV is shown in figure. 4.4. The stability model may developed by identifying the mathematical model for each block [11].

Figure 4.4: Basic SVC model

4.2.5.1 Description of basic model

The basic SVC model consists of the following elements

- **Measuring module**

The characteristics of the measuring circuit and filter circuit can be approximated by the transfer function:

Figure 4.5: Measuring circuit module

- **Voltage regulator module**

Voltage regulator module-Basic Model 1

The gain, K_R , is the reciprocal of the slope setting. K_R is usually between 20 per unit (5% slope) and 100 per unit (1% slope) on the SVC base. The time constant, T_R , is usually between 20 and 150 milliseconds. The lead-lag terms are often zero. For preliminary simulations, phase lead can be used to improve damping of oscillations (at the expense of synchronizing support). The lead-lag terms can also be used to provide adequate phase and gain

margins when high steady state gain is used. Integrators should be non-windup [8].

Figure 4.6: proportional type

Voltage regulator module-Basic Model 2

The proportional gain, if used, results in a faster response. The time constant, T_p , may be zero. The integrator is non-windup

Figure 4.7: Integral

Thyristor susceptance control module

Figure 4.8 shows the CIGRE model for the delays associated with the thyristor firing. T_d is the gating transport delay and T_b represents the effect of thyristor firing sequence control

Figure 4.8: Thyristor susceptance control module

• **Typical parameters of SVC**

The parameters for the SVC have to be selected according to SVC rating and performance criteria taking in to account the power system behavior under various operating conditions and SVC response under such conditions. Typical values for the various SVC models are given below [11].

Module	Parameter	Definition	Typical value
Measuring	T_m	-Measuring circuit time constant	0.001–0.005s
Thyristor Control	T_d T_b	-Gating transport delay -Thyristor firing sequence control delay	0.001s 0.003–0.006s
Voltage Regulator	K_I	-Integrator gain	- K_I is adjusted for a fast and well-damped response based on selection of the slope
Slope	X_{SL}	-Steady state characteristic slope	0.01–0.05 p. u.

Table 4.1: Typical values for the SVC models

4.3 DISTRIBUTION STATIC COMPENSATOR

The distribution static compensator (DSTATCOM), previously referred to as a static condenser (STATCON) or Advanced static VAR compensator (ASVC) or self commutated static VAR compensator is a shunt connected reactive compensation equipment which is capable of generating and/or absorbing reactive power whose output can be varied as to maintain control of specific parameters of the electric power system.

The term static indicates that it is based on solid state power electronic switching devices with no moving or rotating components. The terms synchronous and compensator indicate that it is analogous to an ideal synchronous machine generating a balanced set of 3 sinusoidal phase voltages at fundamental frequencies.

4.3.1 Basic Description of Distribution static compensator

Thus the DSTATCOM typically consists of DC to AC converter employing solid state power electronic switching devices and a set of converter controls varying the DSTATCOM output in order to control specific power system control parameters as shown in Figure 4.9.

Figure 4.9: Typical DSTATCOM overview

4.3.2 Concept of Distribution static compensator

DSTATCOM (Distribution static compensator) is a controlled voltage source connected to a node through impedance which is usually the impedance of the coupling transformer. The basic operation of it is similar to that of a synchronous compensator. If the voltage generated by the compensator U_k is less than the supply voltage U_s then the compensator will act as an inductive load drawing reactive power from the network. Otherwise, if the compensator voltage is higher than the network voltage then DSTATCOM will act as a capacitor generating reactive power into the supply network [12].

4.3.3 V-I characteristics of Distribution static compensator

The DSTATCOM is essentially an alternating voltage source behind a coupling reactance with the corresponding V-I characteristics as shown in figure 4.10. These shows that the DSTATCOM can be operated over its full output current range even at very low, theoretically zero system voltage levels. The compensation at zero system voltage could only be maintained if an external power source would be available to supply the losses of the DSTATCOM and thus keep the DC storage capacitor charged to the required voltage level. With out the external power sources, the DSTATCOM can be operated with full output current at a system voltage at which the necessary real power

can be absorbed from the AC system to keep the storage capacitor charged, without exceeding the current rating of the converter. In practice this minimum voltage is typically between 0.2 p.u. and 0.4 p.u. significantly below the value at which reactive compensation would be meaningful. In other words, the maximum capacitive or inductive output current of the DSTATCOM can be maintained independently of the AC system voltage, and the maximum VAR generation or absorption changes linearly with the AC system voltage [12].

Figure 4.10: V-I characteristics of DSTATCOM

4.3.4 Applications of Distribution static compensator

Initial application of DSTATCOM was primarily for the control of (fundamental frequency) reactive power control and voltage regulation. SVCs have been applied for this purpose earlier. A DSTATCOM has obvious advantages over a SVC as discussed earlier. A major advantage relates to the improved speed of response, capacity for transient overload (up to one second) in addition to the improved performance at reduced voltages. The applications include

- i. Limiting voltage swells caused by capacitor switching
- ii. Reduction of voltage sags due to common feeder faults
- iii. Controlling the voltage fluctuations caused by customer load variations. This reduces voltage flicker substantially.

- iv. Based on the control algorithm, the frequency of mechanical switching operations (involving load tap changing (LTC) transformers and mechanically switched capacitors) is reduced that is beneficial for maintenance.
- v. Increase in the maximum loadability of the system (in particular, increase in the induction motor load that can remain stable through a major disturbance, such as a loss of primary infeed).

Advantages of DSTATCOM over SVC

Unlike in the case of variable impedance type SVC which uses thyristor devices, there are many technical advantages of a DSTATCOM over a SVC. These are primarily:

- i. Faster response
- ii. Requires less space as bulky passive components (such as reactors) are eliminated
- iii. Inherently modular and relocatable
- iv. It can be interfaced with real power sources such as battery, fuel cell or SMES (superconducting magnetic energy storage)
- v. A DSTATCOM has superior performance during low voltage condition as the reactive current can be maintained constant (In a SVC, the capacitive reactive current drops linearly with the voltage at the limit (of capacitive susceptance). It is even possible to increase the reactive current in a DSTATCOM under transient conditions if the devices are rated for the transient overload. In a SVC, the maximum reactive current is determined by the rating of the passive components – reactors and capacitors.

4.3.5 Modeling of DSTATCOM

A simplified Controlled Current Source model, derived from the controlled current source model is shown below, in which the control loop relating to the DSTATCOM droop characteristic is not represented. This is analogous to an IEEE basic type1 SVC model [12].

Figure 4.11: Simplified controlled current source model

4.3.5.1 Description of basic model

In this simplified DSTATCOM model, the current regulator transfer function has a steady state gain of K_0 ($=1/\text{slope}$) to represent the steady state droop, and a first order lead-lag term to represent the dynamics. Typically, T_2 would be expected to be of the order of 15ms.

$$\text{Choosing } T_1 \text{ such that } K_D \left(\frac{T_1}{T_2} \right) = \frac{1}{X}$$

This simplified model consists of the following elements

- **Measuring module**

The characteristics of the measuring circuit and filter circuit can be approximated by a second order transfer function giving a rise time of 15-20ms with acceptable overshoot, e.g.:

$$H(s) = \frac{1}{(1 + 2\zeta T_H s + T_H^2 s^2)}$$

$$\text{With } \zeta = 0.75 \text{ and } T_H = 5\text{ms}$$

- **Voltage regulator module**

The voltage regulator $M(s)$ incorporates integral action and can generally be represented by a transfer function of the form

$$M(s) = \frac{(1 + T_1s)(1 + T_3s)k(1 + Ts)}{(1 + T_2s)(1 + T_4s)s}$$

Where T_1 , T_2 , T_3 , and T_4 are optional lead-lag time constants which may be applied depending up on the particular application

4.4 HARMONIC FILTERS

One of the common ways of controlling harmonic distortion is to place a passive shunt harmonic filter close to the harmonic producing load(s). The harmonic-producing device can generally be viewed as a source of harmonic current. The objective of the harmonic filter is to shunt some of the harmonic current from the load into the filter, thereby reducing the amount of harmonic current that flows into the power system. The simplest type of shunt harmonic filter is a series inductance/capacitance (LC) circuit. More complex harmonic filters may involve multiple LC circuits, some of which may also include a resistor. Some commonly used harmonic filter arrangements are shown. They play a double role: that is, eliminate harmonic currents and reduce the system load by reactive power compensation – for the fundamental harmonic. All filter configurations for this harmonic have a capacitive character.

The filter configuration is individually designed for a given point of supply so as to obtain the required frequency–impedance characteristic of the supply system. Resonant filters, both single frequency and double tuned, guarantee low impedance for selected series resonance frequencies, whereas damped filters have low impedance over a broad frequency range. Hence they are referred to as broadband filters. The most often used configuration is single-frequency resonant filters plus a broadband filter. This, of course, does not exclude other solutions which are technically advantageous and economically viable for specific applications [7].

A shunt filter is said to be tuned to the frequency that makes its inductive and capacitive reactances equal. The quality of a filter (Q) determines the sharpness of tuning and in this respect filters may be either of a high or a low Q type. The former is sharply tuned to one of the lower harmonic frequencies (e.g. the fifth) and a typical value is between 30 and 60. The low Q filter, typically in the region of 0.5–5, has low impedance over a wide range of frequency. When used to eliminate the higher-order harmonics (e.g.

17th up wards) it is also referred to as a high-pass filter. Typical examples of high and low Q filter circuits and their impedance variation with frequency are illustrated in Figures 4.12 and 4.13. In the case of a tuned filter Q is defined as the ratio of the inductance (or the capacitance) to resistance at the resonant frequency, i.e.

$$Q = \frac{X_0}{R}$$

**Figure 4.12: a) Single-tuned shunt filter circuit;
(b) single-tuned shunt filter impedance versus frequency**

**Figure 4.13: a) Second-order damped shunt filter;
(b) second-order damped shunt filter impedance versus frequency**

4.4.1 Filter Design Criteria

Key filter design considerations include the following:

- a) Reactive power requirements
- b) Harmonic limitations
- c) Normal system conditions, including ambient harmonics
- d) Normal harmonic filter conditions
- e) Contingency system conditions, including ambient harmonics
- f) Contingency harmonic filter conditions

The size of a filter is defined as the reactive power that the filter supplies at fundamental frequency. It is substantially equal to the fundamental reactive power supplied by the capacitors. The total size of all the branches of a filter is determined by the reactive power requirements of the harmonic source and by how much this requirement can be supplied by the a.c. network.

Step 1: Determine harmonic filter bank kVAR size

In addition to harmonic filtering, the filter equipment will provide the system with capacitive reactive power that will improve the power factor and help maintain voltage during heavy loads. The capacitive reactive power requirements for power factor and voltage control generally determine the effective kvar. size of the harmonic filter. The effective kvar of the harmonic filter is always less than the nameplate kvar of the harmonic filter capacitor because of the subtractive effect of the filter reactor.

Initial power factor of the system,

$$pf_1 = \frac{P_1}{\sqrt{(P_1^2) + (Q_1^2)}} \quad \text{----- (4.4)}$$

Assume, required power factor of the system is pf_2 ($pf_2 > pf_1$)

$$pf_2 = \frac{P_2}{\sqrt{(P_2^2) + (Q_2^2)}} \quad \text{----- (4.5)}$$

Where, $P_2 = P_1$ and calculate Q_2 using above equation

The effective reactive power of the harmonic filter is

$$Q_{eff} = Q_1 - Q_2 \quad \text{----- (4.6)}$$

Step 2: Select initial harmonic filter tuning

Based on the harmonic generation, an initial estimate of the harmonic filter tuning is made. The tuning is usually designed to reduce harmonic voltage and current distortion to meet specified harmonic performance criteria. To meet this objective, the harmonic filter will typically be tuned to the lowest frequency of the most significant harmonics.

Harmonic filters are not usually tuned to exact harmonic frequencies. Tuning directly to the harmonic frequency may have two undesirable consequences:

- a) The low impedance at resonance can result in nearly all harmonic current at that frequency being absorbed by the harmonic filter. The harmonic filter is required to be larger and more expensive than is needed to achieve the required harmonic performance.
- b) The harmonic filter interaction with the system impedances results in a parallel resonance at a frequency just lower than the tuned frequency. If a harmonic filter is designed exactly at the harmonic frequency, a variation in the impedance values of the actual equipment from the design values could retune the harmonic filter and place the parallel resonant frequency very close to the harmonic. Instead of low impedance, the combined harmonic filter-system impedance becomes resonant at the harmonic frequency, distortion levels become unacceptable, and damaging voltage amplification may result in severe cases.

It is always advantageous to tune the harmonic filter to approximately 3 % to 15 % below the harmonic frequency. This tuning will provide for sufficient harmonic filtering, yet will also provide the allowance for the detuning of the harmonic filter.

The reactance of the harmonic filter capacitor is determined by the VAR size of the harmonic filter

The effective reactance (for a filter tuned to h harmonic) of the harmonic filter at power frequency is given by

$$X_{eff} = \frac{(V_{LL})^2}{Q} \Omega \quad \text{----- (4.7)}$$

The capacitive reactance is given by the following equation

$$X_C = \frac{h^2}{(h^2 - 1)} * X_{eff} \quad \text{----- (4.8)}$$

The inductive reactance is given of the harmonic filter is given by

$$X_L = \frac{X_C}{h^2} \Omega \quad \text{----- (4.9)}$$

Where X_{eff} is the effective reactance of the harmonic filter,

V_{LL} is the nominal system line to line voltage,

X_C is the capacitive reactance of the harmonic filter capacitor at fundamental frequency

X_L is the inductive reactance of the harmonic filter reactor at fundamental frequency

h is harmonic number

Calculate capacitance and inductance by using above equations for fundamental frequency

The quality factor varies between 40 to 80

The resistance is calculated by using

$$R = \frac{1}{Q} \sqrt{\left(\frac{L}{C}\right)} \quad \text{----- (4.10)}$$

If the harmonic filter tuning is chosen to be slightly less than the harmonic frequency as suggested, then h will be non-integer. For example, h will be 4.7 for 5th harmonic.

Step 3: Optimize the harmonic filter configuration to meet harmonic guidelines

IEEE STD 519-1992 provides guidelines for harmonic distortion limits. The harmonic filter must limit both voltage and current distortion over a range of normal system configurations as well as abnormal conditions. The analysis can be done by hand calculations for simple systems. Usually, however, a harmonic simulation program is required to adequately assess each of the possible operating conditions over the frequency spectrum of the harmonic loads. IEEE STD 519-1992 and IEEE STD 399-1997 provide guidance on performing the required studies.

If distortion levels are still too high, it may be because the addition of a harmonic filter has caused a new parallel resonance with the system near one of the lower frequency harmonics. In this case, a retuning of the harmonic filter to the lower harmonic frequency can sometimes be adequate. If it is not, then multiple-tuned harmonic filters may be needed.

bus voltage at PCC	Individual voltage Distortion (%)	Total Voltage Distortion THD (%)
69 kV and below	3	5
69kV to 161 kV	1.5	2.5
160 kV and above	1	1.5

Table 4.2: Typical values of THD at various buses [12]

The broadness of the tuning can be increased to account for capacitance and inductance deviations by increasing the filter kvar size.

4.5 SURGE ARRESTOR

Arresters and TVSS (Transient Voltage Surge Suppressers) devices protect equipment from transient overvoltages by limiting the maximum voltage, and the terms are sometimes used interchangeably. However, TVSSs are generally associated with devices used at the load equipment. A TVSS will sometimes have more surge-limiting elements than an arrester, which most commonly consists solely of MOV blocks. An arrester may have more energy-handling capability.

Overvoltage protection devices or surge protectors protect facilities and equipment against transient voltage surges produced by lightning (μ s), electrostatic discharges (ns), switching (ms) or long voltage deviations at power frequency (s). They limit or eliminate voltage surges up to acceptable limits, blocking or shorting them to earth.

There are different technologies commercially available: silicon components (Zener diode, triac, etc.), metal oxide varistors (known as MOVs) and spark-gap types (the gas arrester type is the most common). They differ in two important facts: clearing time and dissipation of energy. They are listed like faster clearing time devices. In the reverse order, they are listed for higher conducted energy capability. A combination of two or

even three of these technologies is the best solution. Moreover, spark-gaps are the only type that can withstand several lightning strikes. The others are usually destroyed [7].

The elements that make up these devices can be classified by two different modes of operation, crowbar and clamping.

Crowbar devices are normally open devices that conduct current during overvoltage transients. Once the device conducts, the line voltage will drop to nearly zero due to the short circuit imposed across the line. These devices are usually manufactured with a gap filled with air or a special gas. The gap arcs over when a sufficiently high overvoltage transient appears. Once the gap arcs over, usually power frequency current, will continue to flow in the gap until the next current zero. Thus, these devices have the disadvantage that the power frequency voltage drops to zero or to a very low value for at least one-half cycle. This will cause some loads to drop offline unnecessarily.

Clamping devices for ac circuits are commonly nonlinear resistors (varistors) that conduct very low amounts of current until an overvoltage occurs. When a transient occurs then they start to conduct heavily, and their impedance drops rapidly with increasing voltage. These devices effectively conduct increasing amounts of current (and energy) to limit the voltage rise of a surge. They have an advantage over gap-type devices in that the voltage is not reduced below the conduction level when they begin to conduct the surge current. Zener diodes are also used in this application.

The three most common surge arrester technologies employed by utilities are depicted in Figure. 4.14 Most arresters manufactured today use a MOV as the main voltage-limiting element. The chief ingredient of a MOV is zinc oxide (ZnO), which is combined with several proprietary ingredients to achieve the necessary characteristics and durability. Older-technology arresters, of which there are still many installed on the power system, used silicon carbide (SiC) as the energy-dissipating nonlinear resistive element. The relative discharge voltages for each of these three technologies are shown in Figure 4.15.

Figure 4.14: Three common utility surge arrester technologies.

Figure 4.15: Comparative lightning wave discharge voltage characteristics for an 8 X 20 μ s wave corresponding to the utility surge arrester technologies

Originally, arresters were little more than spark gaps, which would result in a fault each time the gap sparked over. Also, the sparkover transient injected a very steep fronted voltage wave into the apparatus being protected, which was blamed for many insulation failures. The addition of SiC nonlinear resistance in series with a spark gap corrected some of these difficulties. It allowed the spark gap to clear and reseal without causing a fault and reduced the sparkover transient to perhaps 50 percent of the total sparkover voltage. However, insulation failures were still blamed on this front-of-wave transient.

Also, there is substantial power-follow current after sparkover, which heats the SiC material and erodes the gap structures, eventually leading to arrester failures or loss of protection. Gaps are necessary with the SiC because an economical SiC element giving the required discharge voltage is unable to withstand continuous system operating voltage. The development of MOV technology enabled the elimination of the gaps. This

technology could withstand continuous system voltage without gaps and still provide a discharge voltage comparable to the SiC arresters (see Figure. 4.15(b)). By the late 1980s, SiC arrester technology was being phased out in favor of the gapless MOV technology. The gapless MOV provided a somewhat better discharge characteristic without the objectionable sparkover transient.

The majority of utility distribution arresters manufactured today are of this design. By combining resistance-graded gaps (with SiC grading rings) and MOV blocks, this arrester technology has some very interesting, and counterintuitive, characteristics. It has a lower lightning-discharge voltage, but has a higher transient overvoltage (TOV) withstand characteristic than a gapless MOV arrester. To achieve the required protective level for lightning, gapless MOV arresters typically begin to conduct heavily for low-frequency transients at about 1.7 pu. There are some system conditions where the switching transients will exceed this value for several cycles and cause failures. Also, applications such as aging underground cable systems demand lower lightning-discharge characteristics.

The gapped MOV technology removes about one-third of the MOV blocks and replaces them with a gap structure having a lightning sparkover approximately one-half of the old SiC technology. The smaller number of MOV blocks yields a lightning-discharge voltage typically 20 to 30 percent less than a gapless MOV arrester. Because of the capacitive and resistive interaction of the grading rings and MOV blocks, most of the front-of-wave impulse voltage of lightning transients appears across the gaps. They spark over very early into the MOV blocks, yielding a minor sparkover transient on the front. For switching transients, the voltage divides by resistance ratios and most of it appears first across the MOV blocks, which hold off conduction until the gaps spark over. This enables this technology to achieve a TOV withstand of approximately 2.0 pu in typical designs.

Additionally, the energy dissipated in the arrester is less than dissipated by gapless designs for the same lightning current because of the lower voltage discharge of the MOV blocks. There is no power-follow current because there is sufficient MOV capability to block the flow. This minimizes the erosion of the gaps. In several ways, this Technology holds the promise of yielding more capable and durable utility surge arrester.

CHAPTER V
SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

CHAPTER V

SIMULATIONS AND RESULTS

This section contains the results of the simulations to assess the capability of each technique to mitigate various Power Quality issues. In order to make a fair assessment, the simulations use only one test system. The test system data is given the appendix.

Description of study system

The study system taken is a 20-bus industrial system. The system taken has 6 generators and connected to grid. In the system taken there is an industry connected at 66 kV. The industry has a motor load connected at 11 kV, and arc furnace load connected to bus-603. These are the instigators of the Power Quality issues viz., voltage sags because of motor starting and harmonics & time varying load (cyclic load) because of the arc furnace. The starting of this large motor is accompanied by voltage sag resulting from the inrush current flowing through the system impedances. During the operation of arc furnace load there is a drastic power variations and cause very large voltage fluctuations and due to the nature of the current drawn by the arc furnace, which is extremely nonlinear, large harmonic currents are also produced. The harmonics produced are of the order 5th, 7th, and 11th. So, arc furnace load is represented by using a cyclic load and harmonic injecting current source.

Separate cases of these major power quality issues are analysed with and with out the compensating devices and simulated by using MiPower.

Case 1

Voltage dip due to Motor starting

The system taken has a motor load, connected at 11 kV

	Connected to bus No	MVA Rating	MW Rating	kV Rating	Inertia
Motor	5	4.6875	3.6	11	500

Table 5.1: Motor data

Without the motor load, the steady state voltage at the motor bus is found to be 0.96 pu (10.56 kV). Transient stability analysis is carried on the system to analyze the effect of motor starting. The motor is started at 1 sec and the bus voltage has immediately dipped to 0.78 from 1 sec to 8 sec i.e., for 7 secs due to the large inrush current taken by the motor. After 7 secs of motor starting, the bus voltage is restored to 0.933 pu and remained constant. The Figures 5.1 & 5.2 shows the behavior of the motor during starting.

Figure 5.1: Voltage at the 11 kV bus (motor is started after 1 sec)

Figure 5.2: Reactive power taken by motor (motor is started after 1 sec)

To reduce the dip, SVC is designed using FPB (Free Programmable Block) in MiPower and connected at motor bus. SVC is designed by using sensitivity based simulations and SVC parameters were finely tuned based on system requirement.

SVC model:

There are mainly two types of models used for SVC, one is integral type and the other one is proportional type. Proportional type is used in this system study.

Min limit = 0

Max limit = 0.4

TCR details:

Filter:

Gain, $K = 1.1$

$T = 0.06$ sec

Non Wind-up limiter:

Min limit = 0

Max limit = 0.4

Fixed capacitor rating:

$B = 0.19$ pu.

Transient stability analysis is carried on the system for the motor starting using SVC. With SVC in service, the bus voltage fell to only 0.94 pu (0.78 pu in case of motor starting without SVC) which shows the effectiveness of SVC in mitigating voltage sags. Further from the study it is observed that the motor starting time is reduced to 4.3 sec (with SVC) from 7 sec (without SVC).

Figure 5.4: Voltage at the 11 kV bus – by using SVC

A DSTATCOM is said to have superior performance during low voltage condition as the reactive current can be maintained constant compared to SVC because in a SVC the capacitive reactive current drops linearly with the voltage at the limit of capacitive susceptance. To validate this fact, the same motor starting study was performed with DSTATCOM. The DSTATCOM is designed using FPB (Free Programmable Block) in MiPower. DSTATCOM is designed by using sensitivity based simulations and DSTATCOM parameters were finely tuned based on system requirement.

The model and its parameters are given below.

DSTATCOM Model:

There are mainly three types of models used for DSTATCOM, controlled voltage source model, controlled current source model and simplified controlled current source model. Simplified controlled current source model is used in this system study [11].

Figure 5.5: DSTATCOM Model designed using FPB

DSTATCOM parameters

Measuring circuit

Filter:

Gain, $K = 1$

$T = 0.1 \text{ sec}$

Voltage regulator:

Gain, $k = 5$

Lag-Lead compensator:

$T1 = 0.012 \text{ sec}$

$T2 = 0.015 \text{ sec}$

Wind-up limiter:

Min limit = -0.25

Max limit = 0.25

Transient stability analysis is carried out on the system for the motor starting using DSTATCOM. By using the DSTATCOM the voltage dip is reduced to 0.96 pu (0.94 pu in case of SVC) and the starting time of the motor is marginally reduced.

Figure 5.6: Voltage at the 11 kV bus – by using DSTATCOM

Case 2

Voltage dip due to LG Fault and 3-phase fault:

Single line-to-ground faults (SLGF) on the utility system are the most common cause of voltage sags in an industrial plant. The utility attempts to clear the fault by opening and closing the faulted circuit using reclosers, which can require from 40 to 60 cycles. The power line experiences voltage sags or total loss of power for the short duration it takes to clear the fault.

So, to mitigate the voltage dip due to these faults SVC and DSTATCOM can be used.

Using the Transient stability study in MiPower, a single line to ground fault has been applied on 11 kV (motor) bus for a duration of 500 msec.

- During the LG fault a voltage dip of about 0.3 pu is observed

Figure 5.7: Voltage at 11 kV bus when SLG fault applied

- By using SVC the dip is reduced to 0.22 pu.

Figure 5.8: voltage at 11 kV bus when SLG fault applied & SVC connected

- By using DSTATCOM the dip is reduced to 0.13 pu

As already mentioned that DSTATCOM has superior performance compared to SVC during low voltage condition as the reactive current can be maintained constant and is independent of the system voltage, the voltage dip is reduced considerably.

Figure 5.9: voltage at 11 kV bus when SLG fault applied & DSTATCOM connected

To test the working of these two devices a 3 phase fault is applied at 11 kV bus.

Figure 5.10: Voltage 11 kV bus when 3-phase fault applied

During the 3-phase fault the 3-phase voltages will be zero. As SVC is a voltage dependent, this does not improve the bus voltage (because the injected reactive power is zero) during symmetrical faults. Figure 5.11 illustrates the same.

Figure 5.11: Voltage at 5th bus when 3-phase fault applied & SVC connected

DSTATCOM can be operated over its full output current range even at very low, theoretically zero system voltage levels. But practically due to limitation in operation of the converter it doesn't. So, the DSTATCOM is also ineffective during 3 phase fault.

Figure 5.12: voltage at 11 kV bus when 3-phase fault applied & DSTATCOM connected

Case 3**Voltage fluctuations due to cyclic load:**

Voltage fluctuations due to cyclic load such as arc furnace load and rolling mills are one of the major Power Quality issue. Arc furnaces impose large electrical power requirements on the electrical system. The current drawn from the source tends to be highly cyclic as arcs are repeatedly struck and stabilized in different parts of the batch. These voltage fluctuations cause flickering. To mitigate these fluctuations industries mostly use SVC and DSTATCOM.

The system taken for study has arc furnace load at 66 kV bus. It is represented as a cyclic load in MiPower. The data of the cyclic load is given below.

S.No	Time (sec)	P(MW)	Q(MVAr)
1	0	0	0
2	10	0	0
3	10.02	10	10
4	20	10	10
5	20.02	20	20
6	40	20	20
7	40.02	20	20
8	50	20	20
9	50.02	0	0
10	60	0	0

Table 5.2: Cyclic load data

Transient stability analysis is carried out on the system by considering this arc furnace load. The voltage at the supply lines to the arc furnace is shown in figure 5.13.

From Figure 5.13 it can be observed

- i. A load of 10 MW & 10 MVAr causes the voltage to drop by 5% (0.05 p.u.)
- ii. A load of 20 MW & 20 MVAr causes the voltage to drop by 10% (0.1 p.u.)

To reduce the voltage fluctuations two cases are considered. In the first case SVC is placed and in the second case DSTATCOM is placed at the bus producing voltage fluctuations and the effectiveness of these two devices in reducing the voltage fluctuations is analysed.

Figure 5.13: 66 kV bus voltage with Arc Furnace load

Figure 5.14: 66 kV bus voltage with Arc furnace load and SVC

Figure 5.15: 66 kV bus voltage with Arc furnace load and DSTATCOM

The following observations can be made from the transient stability analysis

Time	Load (MW+jMVar)	66 kV bus Voltage in pu		
		w/o compensation	With SVC	With DSTATCOM
0 to 10 sec	(0 + j 0)	0.994	1.01	1.00
10 to 20 sec	(10 + j 10)	0.953	1.01	0.98
20 to 50 sec	(20 + j 20)	0.9	0.958	0.962
50 to 60 sec	(0 + j 0)	0.994	1.01	0.98

Table 5.3: voltage at 66 kV bus without compensating device, with SVC and with DSTATCOM

From the above observations we can say that the bus voltage fluctuations are reduced considerably by using SVC and DSTATCOM.

Case (4)**Harmonic mitigation**

The study system taken has arc furnace load injecting harmonics into system at bus number 603. This is represented as harmonic injecting current source in MiPower.

The harmonic source data is given in the table below.

Harmonic Number	Phase A		Phase B		Phase C	
	Current(A)	Angle	Current(A)	Angle	Current(A)	Angle
5	20	0	20	120	20	-120
7	15	0	15	120	15	-120
11	10	0	10	120	10	-120

Table 5.4: current harmonic source data

The system is analysed by conducting the harmonic analysis using POWERHAR module in MiPower. Because of the harmonic source the voltage harmonic distortion at bus-5 (11 kV) is 7.987, at bus-603 & bus- 5115 (66 kV) is 5.7 which is not acceptable. According to IEEE STD 519-1992 voltage harmonic distortion below 69 kV must be less than 5 %. The table below shows the harmonic distortion at various buses in the system.

Voltage (kV)	Node name	%HDF-A	%HDF-B	%HDF-B	%HDF-AVR
11	1 bus1	0.2523	0.2709	0.2449	0.2563
11	2 bus2	0.2523	0.2709	0.2449	0.2563
11	3 bus3	0.2523	0.2709	0.2449	0.2563
11	4 bus4	0.2523	0.2709	0.2449	0.2563
11	5 bus5	7.9873	7.9873	7.9874	7.9873
21	6 bus6	0.2297	0.2297	0.2297	0.2297
21	7 bus7	0.2297	0.2297	0.2297	0.2297
220	201 bus201	0.5233	0.5233	0.5233	0.5233
220	202 bus202	1.9714	1.9714	1.9714	1.9714
220	203 bus203	0.4948	0.4948	0.4948	0.4948
220	204 bus204	0.1927	0.1927	0.1927	0.1927
400	401 bus401	0.3827	0.3828	0.3827	0.3827
400	402 bus402	0.5901	0.5902	0.5902	0.5901
66	601 bus601	3.6595	3.6595	3.6595	3.6595
66	602 bus602	3.8462	3.8462	3.8462	3.8462
66	603 bus603	5.6993	5.6993	5.6993	5.6993
66	604 bus604	3.6595	3.6595	3.6595	3.6595
66	605 bus605	0.1927	0.1927	0.1927	0.1927
66	610 Switch	3.8461	3.8461	3.8461	3.8461
11	5115 CAPBUS	7.9874	7.9874	7.9875	7.9874

Table 5.5: Total Voltage distortion at different buses without harmonic filter

Figure 5.16: Total voltage harmonic distortion at different buses without harmonic filter

To reduce the voltage harmonic distortion a harmonic filter is designed.

As already discussed, the harmonic filter rating is taken as the amount of reactive power required to improve the power factor.

Calculation of filter parameters for the study system

Initial Real and reactive power of the load is $P_1 = 12$ MW, $Q_1 = 5.811$ MVA

Initially, the power factor of the industrial system with out filter is 0.9

$$\text{i.e., } pf_1 = 0.9$$

To improve the power factor from 0.9 to 0.95, we require reactive power of

$$Q_2 = 3.944 \text{ MVA}$$

So, the reactive power to be compensated by the filter to improve the power factor from 0.9 to 0.95 is,

$$Q_{eff} = Q_1 - Q_2 = 5.8 - 3.9 = 1.9 \approx 2 \text{ MVA}$$

The reactive power to be compensated is distributed between the filters based on the harmonic content

Harmonic number	5 th	7 th	11 th
-----------------	-----------------	-----------------	------------------

Reactive power (MVar)	1	0.67	0.33
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Table 5.6: MVar rating of the harmonic filters**Specimen calculations for 3rd harmonic**

$$X_{eff} = \frac{(V_{LL})^2}{Q} \Omega = 66^2 / 1 = 4356 \Omega$$

$$X_{C1} = \frac{1}{2\pi f C_1} \Rightarrow C_1 = 0.7 \mu\text{F}$$

$$X_L = \frac{X_C}{h_n^2} = 4356/5^2 = 174.24 \Omega$$

$$X_{L1} = 2\pi f L_1 \Rightarrow L_1 = 554 \text{ mH}$$

Taking Quality factor Q= 60, then

$$R = \frac{1}{Q} \sqrt{\left(\frac{L}{C}\right)} = 14.52 \Omega$$

By using the above procedure the components of the remaining filters are calculated

Figure 5.17: Single tuned filter designed for the harmonics considered

After performing the loadflow and harmonic analysis, by placing the designed harmonic filter near arc furnace load, the voltage harmonic distortion is reduced

considerably i.e., 1.4 % at 11 kV level and 1 % at 66 kV level. This is within the IEEE STD 519 recommended limits i.e., less than 5% below 69 kV.

Figure 5.18: Total voltage harmonic distortion at different buses with harmonic filter

Case (5)

Transient overvoltages mitigation

Lightning is a potent source of impulsive transients which is also a major power quality issue. The lightning surges enter loads from the utility system through the interwinding capacitance of the service transformer as shown in Figure. 5.19. The concept is that the lightning impulse is so fast that the inductance of the transformer windings blocks the first part of the wave from passing through by the turns ratio. However, the interwinding capacitance may offer a ready path for the high-frequency surge. This can permit the existence of a voltage on the secondary terminals that is much higher than what the turns ratio of the windings would suggest [1].

Figure 5.19: Coupling of impulses through the interwinding capacitance of transformers.

Surge suppression devices should be located as closely as possible to the critical insulation with a minimum of lead length on all terminals. While it is common to find arresters located at the main panels and subpanels, arresters applied at the point where the power line enters the load equipment are generally the most effective in protecting that particular load. MV lines are generally more exposed to lightning flashes than LV lines: they have longer and higher structures than other structures located in their vicinity (houses, trees).

Here the system is reduced to design a surge arrester for a transformer and the worst case is considered here i.e., if the lightning transient falls near the transformer.

As discussed earlier during lightning, the transients enter loads from the utility system through the interwinding capacitance of the service transformer, so the transformer is modeled in detail [13] and represented by using interwinding capacitance and high voltage to ground and low voltage to ground capacitance. For cable the parameters are designed by taking surge impedance of 25Ω and velocity as $1.9e8$ m/sec.

The value of the capacitance is taken from the reference [13]

Transformer MVA	C_{hg}	C_{hl}	C_{lg}
1	1.2-14	1.2-17	3.1-16
2	1.2-16	1-18	3-16
5	1.2-14	1.1-20	5.5-17
10	4-7	4-11	8-18
25	2.8-4.2	2.5-18	5.2-20
50	4-6.8	3.4-11	3-24
75	3.5-7	5.5-13	2.8-13

Table 5.7: Typical capacitance of core-form Transformers (Capacitance in nF)

For the 75 MVA, 220/66 kV transformer in the system corresponding capacitances average are taken i.e.,

$$C_{hg} = 5 \text{ nF}, C_{hl} = 9 \text{ nF}, C_{lg} = 8 \text{ nF}$$

And are converted in to susceptance in p.u. and given in MiPower

A standard current impulse of amplitude 20 kA, 8/20 μ s is applied at bus-3.

Figure 5.20: System taken for lightning transient study

- Due to the lightning stroke, transient voltage of 11.84 p.u. at HV bus & 10.94 p.u. at LV bus is observed, which damages most of the equipment in the system and this is out of the acceptable BIL (Basic Impulse insulation Level) rating (For 220kV it can be up to 950 kV & For 66kV it can be up to 325 kV)

BIL is Basic Impulse Level, sometimes referred to as "Basic Insulation Level". It represents the "strength" of equipment's insulation for a high-voltage impulse.

Figure 5.21: Voltage at 3rd bus when a current impulse applied

Figure 5.22: Voltage at Transformer HV bus when a current impulse applied

Figure 5.23: Voltage at Transformer LV bus when a current impulse applied

Highest voltage for Equipment U_M (kV rms)	Standardized short-duration with stand frequency voltage at power frequency (kV rms)	Standardized with stand voltage to lightning impulses (kV rms)
3.6	10	20/40
7.2	20	40/60
12	28	60/75/95
17.5	38	75/95
24	50	95/125/145
36	70	145/170
52	95	250
72.5	145	325
123	(185)230	450/550
145	185/230/275	(450)/550/650
170	(230)/275/325	(550)/650/750
245	(275)/(325)/360/395/460	(650)/(750)/850/950/1050

Table 5.8: Standardized insulation levels for R.M.S. voltage networks between 1 & 245 kV

To reduce the impulse voltages at the buses a 180 kV surge arrester is designed and placed at 11 kV bus. The Surge arrester V-I characteristics are calculated and given in the MiPower input file. The surge arrestors V-I characteristics are taken from Reference [14]; the peak values given are converted in to p.u. values based on 100 MVA, 220 kV base and are given in MiPower.

V _{p.u.}	I _{p.u.}
1.25	1e-003
2.17	0.808
2.26	1.616
2.319	2.42
2.41	4.04
2.54	8.08
2.78	16.16
3.04	32.2

Table 5.9: V-I characteristics of Surge Arrester

- By placing the surge arrester at 11 kV bus the transient level is reduced and the voltage transients are reduced to 2.76 pu (607.2 kV) on HV side and to 2.52 pu (166.32 kV) on the LV side, which is within the acceptable BIL level (For 220kV it can be up to 3.06 pu (950 kV) & for 66kV it can be up to 325 kV).

Figure 5.24: Voltage at Transformer HV bus when a current impulse applied and surge arrester connected

Figure 5.25: Voltage at Transformer LV bus when a current impulse applied and surge arrester connected

CHAPTER VI
CONCLUSION

CHAPTER VI

CONCLUSION

6.1 CONCLUSION

Nowadays, reliability and quality of electric power is one of the most discussed topics in power industry. There are numerous types of Power Quality issues and power problems and each of them might have varying and diverse causes. The types of Power Quality problems that a customer may encounter classified depending on how the voltage waveform is being distorted. There are transients, short duration variations (sags, swells and interruption), long duration variations (sustained interruptions, under voltages, over voltages), voltage imbalance, waveform distortion (dc offset, harmonics, interharmonics, notching, and noise), voltage fluctuations and power frequency variations. Among them, three Power Quality problems have been identified to be of major concern to the customers are voltage sags, harmonics and transients. This project is focusing on these major issues.

Voltage sags are huge problems for many industries, and it is probably the most pressing Power Quality problem today. Voltage sags may cause tripping and large torque peaks in electrical machines. Generally, voltage sags are short duration reductions in rms voltage caused by faults in the electric supply system and the starting of large loads, such as motors. Voltage sags are also generally created on the electric system when faults occur due to lightning, which are accidental shorting of the phases by trees, animals, birds, human error such as digging underground lines or automobiles hitting electric poles, and failure of electrical equipment. Sags also may be produced when large motor loads are started, or due to operation of certain types of electrical equipment such as welders, arc furnaces, smelters, etc.

Therefore, this project intends to investigate mitigation technique that is suitable for different type of voltage sags source, voltage fluctuations, harmonics and transients. The simulation will be using MiPower software and the mitigation techniques that using such as Static VAR Compensator (SVC), Distribution static compensator (DSTATCOM), passive Harmonic Filters, and Surge arrestor.

SVC and DSTATCOM are used to protect sensitive loads from the effects of voltage sags on the distribution feeder. These devices are placed in shunt with a sensitive load, must be able to respond quickly to voltage sag if end users of sensitive equipment are to experience no voltage sags.

The distribution static compensator (DSTATCOM) offers good shunt compensation. In the traditional power transmission system, controllable devices are restricted to the slow mechanisms such as transformer tap changers and switched capacitor. In the late 1980's, thanks to the major developments in the semiconductor technology, it became possible to apply power electronics in the control of DSTATCOM. Based on the simulation, there's a room for improvement. DSTATCOM is a device that promises a prominent feature in power system in mitigating Power Quality related problems.

Harmonic filters are considered to be a good solution for eliminating certain harmonics and additional advantage of providing reactive power at fundamental frequency. This is a cost effective solution and mostly used in the industries.

Finally, surge arrestors are used to divert lightning transients and switching transients to the ground with out much effect on the equipment connected to the system.

As conclusion, these Power Quality issues are unwanted phenomenon which are unavoidable but can be reduced using all techniques, but not limited to the techniques that have been discussed. There is no one mitigation technique that will suitable with every application, and whilst the power supply utilities strive to supply improved Power Quality, it is up to the applications engineer to minimize Power Quality problems. It means, Power Quality problem cannot be eliminated but we can reduce and try to avoid this problem form occur. The best way to avoid Power Quality problem is by ensuring that all equipment to be installed in the industrial plants are compatible with Power Quality in the power system. This can be achieved by procuring equipment with proper technical specifications that incorporate Power Quality performance of its operating electrical environment.

6.2 SCOPE FOR THE FUTURE WORK

Mitigating Power Quality issues requires a lot of intensive research especially in developing custom power device to help distribution system to achieve desired power quality has been insisted by many customer or end-user. There are still rooms of improvement that can be achieved further, for the technique that have been included in this thesis and other techniques that are available.

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APPENDICES:

A. Generator data

	Gen 1	Gen 2	Gen 3	Gen 4	Gen 5	Gen 6
Connected to bus no.	1[bus 1]	2[bus 2]	3[bus 3]	4[bus 4]	6[bus 6]	7[bus 7]
MVA	137.5	137.5	137.5	137.5	295	295
MW	110	110	110	110	250	250
MVA _r	0<Q<82.5	0<Q<82.5	0<Q<82.5	0<Q<82.5	0<Q<156.6	0<Q<187.5
kV	11	11	11	11	21	21
Scheduled Power	100	100	100	100	200	200
R _a	0.00102	0.00102	0.00102	0.00102	0.001	0.001
X _d	1.479	1.479	1.479	1.479	1.897	1.897
X _q	1.3354	1.3354	1.3354	1.3354	1.8	1.8
X _n	0.1382	0.1382	0.1382	0.1382	0.2	0.2
X _o	0.0861	0.0861	0.0861	0.0861	0.1	0.1
X _p	0.1837	0.1837	0.1837	0.1837	0.23	0.23
X' _d	0.182	0.182	0.182	0.182	0.228	0.228
X' _q	0.383	0.383	0.383	0.383	0.495	0.495
X'' _d	0.1316	0.1316	0.1316	0.1316	0.186	0.186
X'' _q	0.1448	0.1448	0.1448	0.1448	0.205	0.205
T' _{do}	7.15	7.15	7.15	7.15	6.69	6.69
T' _{qo}	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5	2.5
T'' _{do}	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.039	0.03	0.03
T'' _{qo}	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.15	0.05	0.05
'H' in MJ/MVA	3.31	3.31	3x.31	X	3.5	3.5

Type of Modelling	Sub Transient modeling	
AVR Type	1 [AVR 1] Type 1	1 [AVR 1] Type 1
Governor Type	1 Type 1	1 Type 1

B. Grid data

Connected to bus no.	bus Voltage In kV	3-Phase Fault MVA	1-Phase Fault MVA
204 [bus 204]	220	5000	5000

C. Load data

	Connected to bus No	Real Power in 'MW'	Reactive Power In 'MVAR'	Power Factor
Load 1	5	5	2.421611	0.9
Load 2	605	40	19.372884	0.9
Load 3	603	12	5.811865	0.9
Load 4	604	12	5.811865	0.9
Load 5	204	80	26.294728	0.95
Load 6	203	100	32.868411	0.95
Load 7	602	5	2.421611	0.9
Load 8	601	20	9.686442	0.9
Load 9	202	100	48.43221	0.9
Load 10	402	400	193.728842	0.9

D. Transformer data

T/F	From	MVA	Primary	secondary	Nominal	Pos. Seq.	Pos.	Winding
-----	------	-----	---------	-----------	---------	-----------	------	---------

Name	bus-To bus No	Rating	voltage	voltage	Tap Position	Impedance	Seq. R/X	Configuration
T/F1	201 to 1	135	220	11	5	0.14	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Delta
T/F2	201 to 2	135	220	11	5	0.14	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Delta
T/F3	201 to 3	135	220	11	5	0.14	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Delta
T/F4	201 to 4	135	220	11	5	0.14	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Delta
T/F5	401 to 201	315	400	220	5	0.125	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Star grnd
T/F6	401 to 6	300	400	21	5	0.13	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Delta
T/F7	401 to 7	300	400	21	5	0.13	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Delta
T/F8	402 to 203	315	400	220	5	0.125	20	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Star grnd
T/F9	204 to 605	75	220	66	13	0.1	15	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Star grnd
T/F10	202 to 601	75	220	66	13	0.1	15	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Star grnd
T/F11	602 to 5	10	66	11	5	0.08	10	Pri-Star grnd Sec-Star grnd

E. Shunt Capacitor data

	Connected To bus	MVA Rating	Voltage in 'kV'	Pos Seq Susceptance	Zero Seq Susceptance
Shunt Capacitor	5115	3	11	1	1

SIMULATION OF CERTAIN POWER QUALITY ISSUES: VOLTAGE SAGS, HARMONICS & TRANSIENT

	From bus-To bus No	MVA	Line name	Line Length	Pos Seq 'R'	Pos Seq 'X'	Pos Seq 'B/2'	Zero Seq 'R'	Zero Seq 'X'	Zero Seq 'B/2'	
G. Shunt Reactor data	T/L 1	201-202	228	Zebra 220kV	150	0.0748746	0.3992516	1.47E-06	0.219976	1.339228	9.20E-07
	T/L 2	201-202	228	Zebra 220KV	150	0.0748746	0.3992516	1.47E-06	0.219976	1.339228	9.20E-07
	T/L 3	401-402	500	Twin Moose 400kV	300	0.029792	0.332	1.73E-06	0.16192	1.24	1.12E-06
	T/L 4	401-402	500	Twin Moose 400kV	300	0.029792	0.332	1.73E-06	0.16192	1.24	1.12E-06
	T/L 5	203-204	150	Zebra 220kV	100	0.0748746	0.3992516	1.47E-06	0.219976	1.339228	9.20E-07
	T/L 7	601-603	100	Dog	10	0.3	0.4	0	0.6	1.2	0
	T/L 8	601-604	100	Dog	20	0.3	0.4	0	0.6	1.2	0
	T/L 9	203-204	150	Zebra 220kV	100	0.0748746	0.3992516	1.47E-06	0.219976	1.339228	9.20E-07
	T/L 10	601-610	100	Dog	15	0.3	0.4	0	0.6	1.2	0
	T/L 111	202-203	200	Zebra 220kV	200	0.0748746	0.3992516	1.47E-06	0.219976	1.339228	9.20E-07

						Magnetizing Curve Data
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	Connected To bus	MVA Rating	Voltage in 'kV'	Pos Seq Reactance (ohm)	Zero Seq Reactance (ohm)	Knee Point Flux	Pos Seq Reactance (ohm)	Zero Seq Reactance (ohm)
Shunt Reactor1	401	100	420	1	1	1.5	0.3333	0.3333
Shunt Reactor2	402	100	420	1	1	1.5	0.3333	0.3333

H. Transmission line & cable data for overvoltage study system

Conductor type	MVA	Pos Seq Resistance (ohm/km/ckt)	Pos Seq Reactance (ohm/km/ckt)	Pos Seq B/2 (ohm/km/ckt)	Zero Seq Resistance (ohm/km/ckt)	Zero Seq Reactance (ohm/km/ckt)	Zero Seq B/2 (ohm/km/ckt)
Zebra 220kV	100	0.0748746	0.3992516	1.47E-06	0.219976	1.339228	9.20E-07
Cable;XLPE; 200 kV	100	0	0.02616	2.09e-5	0	0.02616	2.09e-5

I. Data for surge arrester V-I characteristics [14]

Max. System Voltage U _m kV _{rms}	Rated Voltage U _r kV _{rms}	Max. continuous operating voltage 1)		TOV capability 2)		Max. residual voltage with current wave						
		as per IEC		as per ANSI/IEEE		30/60 μs			8/20 μs			
		U _c kV _{rms}	MCOV kV _{rms}	1 s kV _{rms}	10 s kV _{rms}	1 kA kV _{peak}	2 kA kV _{peak}	3 kA kV _{peak}	5 kA kV _{peak}	10 kA kV _{peak}	20 kA kV _{peak}	40 kA kV _{peak}
36 ⁹	30	24.0	24.4	34.8	33.0	58.5	60.7	62.2	64.9	68.3	74.8	81.9
	33	26.4	26.7	38.2	36.3	64.4	66.7	68.4	71.4	75.1	82.3	90.1
	36	28.8	29.0	41.7	39.6	70.2	72.8	74.6	77.9	81.9	89.7	98.3
	39	31.2	31.5	45.2	42.9	76.1	78.8	80.8	84.3	88.8	97.2	107
52	42	34	34.0	48.7	46.2	81.9	84.9	87.0	90.8	95.6	105	115
	48	38	39.0	55.6	52.8	93.6	97.0	99.4	104	110	120	132
	54	43	43.0	62.6	59.4	106	110	112	117	123	135	148
	60	48	48.0	69.6	66.0	117	122	125	130	137	150	164
72	54	43	43.0	62.6	59.4	106	110	112	117	123	135	148
	60	48	48.0	69.6	66.0	117	122	125	130	137	150	164
	66	53	53.4	76.5	72.6	129	134	137	143	151	165	181
	72	58	58.0	83.5	79.2	141	146	150	156	164	180	197
	75	60	60.7	87.0	82.5	147	152	156	163	171	187	205
	78	62	63.1	90.4	85.8	153	158	162	169	178	195	213
	84	67	68.0	97.4	92.4	164	170	174	182	192	210	230
	90	72	72.0	104	99.0	176	182	187	195	205	225	246
100	84	67	68.0	97.4	92.4	164	170	174	182	192	210	230
	90	72	72.0	104	99.0	176	182	187	195	205	225	246
	96	77	77.0	111	105	188	194	199	208	219	240	263
123	90	72	72.0	104	99.0	176	182	187	195	205	225	246
	96	77	77.0	111	105	188	194	199	208	219	240	263
	108	78	84.0	125	118	211	219	224	234	246	270	295
	120	78	98.0	139	132	234	243	249	260	273	299	328
	132	78	106	153	145	258	267	274	286	301	329	361
	138	78	111	160	151	270	279	286	299	314	344	377
145	108	86	86.0	125	118	211	219	224	234	246	270	295
	120	92	98.0	139	132	234	243	249	260	273	299	328
	132	92	106	153	145	258	267	274	286	301	329	361
	138	92	111	160	151	270	279	286	299	314	344	377
	144	92	115	167	158	281	291	299	312	328	359	394
170	132	106	106	153	145	258	267	274	286	301	329	361
	144	108	115	167	158	281	291	299	312	328	359	394
	150	108	121	174	165	293	304	311	325	342	374	410
	162	108	131	187	178	316	328	336	351	369	404	443
	168	108	131	194	184	328	340	348	364	383	419	459
245	180	144	144	208	198	351	364	373	390	410	449	492
	192	154	154	222	211	375	388	398	415	437	479	525
	198	156	160	229	217	387	400	410	428	451	494	541
	210	156	170	243	231	410	425	435	454	478	524	574
	216	156	174	250	237	422	437	448	467	492	539	590
	219	156	177	254	240	427	443	454	474	499	546	598
	228	156	180	264	250	445	461	473	493	519	568	623

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